

EVALUATION OF VOCATIONAL EXPERIENCES OF FOOTBALL COACHES AND THEIR VISIONS ABOUT THE PROFESSION

Muazzez Şaşmaz Ataçoğu¹,
Mehmet Mustafa Yorulmazlar

Marmara University
Faculty of Sport Sciences,
Turkey

Abstract:

Football coaches are those who prepare teams for various competitions in technical, tactical, conditioning, strategy and mental contexts by using academic knowledge and experience, and also decide match squad. Football coaches are responsible for the sporting success of the team. Nowadays, a coach is no longer just a technical and tactical coach. From this point of view, football coaching can also be regarded as football business, where the risks associated with professional career are taken the most. Football whose commercial value is increasing day by day is confronted as a workplace where various labor markets take place. In football, labor markets around coaching profession, similar to other labor markets but shaped by the specific characteristics of the profession many experiences are gained by coaches. The aim of this study is to make a general evaluation of the football coach labor market by taking the football coaching profession in the context of the experience of the coaches through their experiences and opinions. Questionnaire technique was applied to obtain data on professional experiences of football coaches in the survey. Survey questions were prepared by us. The obtained data were evaluated in SPSS statistical program and analyzed by frequency and cross tabulation. From this point of view, research is a descriptive model-based research for revealing the general situation of the market. In the findings section of the study, demographic characteristics related to the performance of the coaching profession such as coach license grades, football histories, and educational status are regarded. The quantitative and qualitative findings are related to their professional experience. Although the results of the survey show that

¹ Correspondence: email m.sasmazatacocugu@gmail.com

football coaches are exposed to practices outside of the regulations related to their working life, that these experiences cause social and economic insecurity, that these regulations, which classify coaches and determine the scope and duration of their work, also cause a number of grievances, experience unemployment at various times, that they do not feel secure, that they are unemployed at any moment, and that they have gone through long steps to practice their profession.

Keywords: football coach, employment, unemployment, contractual duration, professional experience

1. Introduction

Football coaches are one of the main actors in football labor market. The professional processes of football coaches are regulated by the Turkish football federation through the "*Instruction of Training and Classification of Technical Men*" and "*Instruction on the Status and Working Principles of Technical Men*". Amateur Technical Man in the Teaching and Classification of Technical Managers Technical Officers and coaches who do not pay any fees except for the expenses (accommodation, materials, insurance and training expenses) related to participation in the football activity and have a written contract with the club, "*Personnel who are licensed or accepted by the TFF who have graduated from courses organized by the TFF and who have received a license from the club and who have a written contract with the club in addition to the obligatory expenses related to participation in the football activity*". (2016, md.2.e, f, g) The Technical Man in the Instruction and Classification of Technical Managers Instructor express "*Technical responsible, coach and amateur coaches*".

Apart from these definitions that determine the statutory of the football coach, the coach is defined as "*a sports person who guides the athletes to their competencies, prepares them, prepares the contests, and leads the sport*" by combining his theoretical knowledge with his experience (Doğan, 2004). Coaches are responsible for the technical management and execution of football teams. For this reason, a coach should have administrative skills as well as technical aspects. This coach is the product of knowledge, experience, and personality. Targeted training and successful team management require extensive professional knowledge (Erdem, 2005). According to another definition, "*A coach is not just about exercising or showing how a sport is done. After he/she interprets the information he receives from sports scientists, sports physicians, and sports psychologists and then compares them with his own experience, he transfers the athlete. Because the data of scientists are theoretical information, they are not suitable for practical application.*"

These data, according to the athletes' personality and sportive characteristics, must undergo some changes" (Başer, 1986). At the same time, in the evaluation of desired changes, effects of age, sport branches and gender of athletes should also be taken into account (Kızılet Bozdoğan and Güler, 2017).

Coaches in Turkish football labor market are classified as follows: UEFA PRO licensed coach, UEFA licensed coach, UEFA B licensed coach, UEFA B licensed coach, TFFA goalkeeper coach, TFF B goalkeeper coach, TFF coach, TFFA licensed coach, TFF B licensed coach, TFF Grassroots C Licensed Coach, TFF Grassroots Volunteer Leader, Futsal Coach, Beach Football Coach, Children's Football Coach, Disabled Football Coach, Match and Performance Analysis Expert, Athletic Performance (Fitness), Player and Match Tracking Expert (Scout)ⁱⁱ. The study areas are arranged in such a way that they will be divided into the league categories according to the license documents they have. In order to be employed as an amateur or professional club as a football coach, it is necessary to have a certificate of a license of the appropriate coach in the respective league.

It is seen that most of the football coaches in Turkey are engaged in the football profession in various league categories before they start their profession. On the basis of this, scores given to the football history can be shown in the application score for coach license coursesⁱⁱⁱ. At the same time, it is also scored to be a graduate and master graduate in the field of football specialty from the Schools of Physical Education and Sports and the Faculty of Sports Sciences, formerly known as the Physical Education and Sports Schools, to have a doctorate and to participate voluntarily in Turkish Football Federation organizations. Football coaches experience many conditions specific to the market up to the time of signing a club agreement and a contract on the football market, where the number of coaches is relatively small but the number of clubs is relatively small, in order to be able to be employed as a coach. Considering that there are 126 football clubs in the professional leagues in 2017/2018 season, 159 football clubs in the Regional Amateur League^{iv} and 98 football clubs in the Super Amateur League, at least 3 coaches, including goalkeeper coaches, are employed in these clubs, it is obvious that some of the coaches will be unemployed. The professional tendency of amateur leagues (Zelyurt and Şaşmaz Ataçoçuğu, 2014) and unregistered verbal agreements (Zelyurt and Şaşmaz Ataçoçuğu, 2016) are the reason why amateur football clubs are taken into account in the employment of football coaches. Amateur leagues have hidden professionalism in terms of footballers and coaches.

ⁱⁱ Instruction of Training and Classification of Technical Men, article.3.

ⁱⁱⁱ Instruction of Training and Classification of Technical Men, appendix, p.20-33.

^{iv} www.tff.org, Date of Access: 03.11.2017

Football coaches' vocational experiences take form around the limitation of not being able to negotiate with more than 2 clubs^v which is interrogated and mostly complained about by coaches, the league category classifications where working can be determined on according to the licenses of the coaches (Şaşmaz Ataçoçu and Zelyurt, 2016), for a variety of reasons specific to the functioning of the market and individual characteristics of the coaches unable to agree or remain idle (unemployed) or within the season the process of terminating the contracts by clubs or releasing their clubs. As a result of this, football coaching is a process that can be experienced in various stages. In this study, football coaching profession and football coaching are examined in the context of their experience in this profession. Through the experience and opinions of the coaches, the aim is to carry out a general evaluation of market of the football coaches.

2. Method

Survey technique was applied to obtain data on professional experiences of football coaches in the survey. The questionnaire was prepared by using the studies of the specific problems related to the working life of the coaches made by Şaşmaz Ataçoçu and Zelyurt (2013, 2016). The questions are multiple choice and the questionnaire was applied by adding an open-ended question in order to receive special opinions about the profession of the football coaches at the end. The data obtained from the field were evaluated in SPSS statistical program and analyzed by frequency and cross tabulation. The open-ended question is given separately in the findings of the study. The questionnaire was applied to 140 football coaches who constitute the sample of the survey. Simple coincidental sampling is used and it is taken into consideration that coaches should be unemployed or active coaches, have any coaching licenses or have experienced coaching.

Determination of the sample of the survey is important in terms of evaluating the labor market while the process coincides with the anxiety of representation of the main mass. From this point of view, research is a descriptive model-based one to reveal the general condition of the research market and it has a clue as to what needs to be done to improve the market.

In the findings of the study, data of open-ended questions are numbered as P1, P2, P3 ..., P140 (participant) for each coach.

^v Instruction on the Status and Working Principles of Technical Men, 2010, article.6/5

3. Findings

3.1 Demographic Features

Coaches who participated in the survey, 4.3% (6 of them) were in the age range 18-23, 12.9% (18 of them) 24-29, 12.1% (17 of them) 30-35 years, 23.6% (33 of them) is in the age range of 36-41, 47.1% (66 of them) is 42 years old and above.

Table 1: Football Coaches According To Licenses

Which coaching license do you have?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	TFF Grassroots C	27	19,3	19,3	19,3
	UEFA B	25	17,9	17,9	37,1
	UEFA A	32	22,9	22,9	60,0
	UEFA Pro	12	8,6	8,6	68,6
	Coach	1	,7	,7	69,3
	TFF C	21	15,0	15,0	84,3
	TFF B	6	4,3	4,3	88,6
	TFF A	2	1,4	1,4	90,0
	Any of these licenses + goalkeeper coaching	14	10,0	10,0	100,0
	Total	140	100,0	100,0	

19.3% (27 of them) of the coaches participating in the survey have TFF Grassroots C, 17.9% (25 of them) have UEFA B, 22.9% (32 of them) have UEFA A and 8.6% (12 of them) have UEFA Pro coaching licenses.

Table 2: Leagues Coaches Work According to Their Licenses

		Which league you are currently coaching?								Total
		Region amateur league	One of the amateur leagues	Professional team pro-leagues	3rd. league	2nd. league	1st. league	I am currently doing a job other than coaching	I am not doing any work right now	
Which coaching license do you have?	TFF Grassroots C	1	15	4	0	1	1	5	0	27
	UEFA B	2	15	1	3	0	0	2	2	25
	UEFA A	2	5	9	4	0	0	9	3	32
	UEFA Pro	1	2	1	1	0	0	2	5	12
	Coach	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
	TFF C	0	15	0	0	1	0	3	2	21

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	TFF B	0	3	1	0	0	0	2	0	6
	TFF A	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
	Any of these licenses + goalkeeper coaching	1	1	5	3	1	1	1	1	14
Total		7	57	21	11	3	2	24	15	140

5% (7 of them) of the coaches participating in the survey are currently in any of Region Amateur League, 40.7% (57 of them) are in any of amateur leagues, 15% (21 of them) are in any of professional team pro-leagues, 7% (11 of them) are in the third league, 2.1% (3 of them) are in the second league and 1.4% (2 of them) are in the first league. 17,1% (24 of them) are currently doing business than football coaching, while 10,7% (15 of them) are currently doing no work. P(31) "I want this job to be called as a profession now." P(56) "Coaching is not regarded as a profession in Turkey, so it would be good to conduct studies on this subject."

Table 3: Background of Football Coaches

Have you played football before your coaching career?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Professional	54	38,6	38,6	38,6
	Amateur	60	42,9	42,9	81,4
	Both	26	18,6	18,6	100,0
	Total	140	100,0	100,0	

38.6% (54 of them) of the coaches participating in the survey stated that they were the professional footballer before starting to be a coach while 42.9% (60 of them) were amateur footballer. P(21) "There is already a monotone environment. I personally did not get what I deserved. I even have 10 years of professional football life."

Table 4: Educational Status Related to Football

Are you graduate of the Faculty of Physical Education and Sports / Sports Sciences Faculty specializing at football?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Yes	41	29,3	29,3	29,3
	No	99	70,7	70,7	100,0
	Total	140	100,0	100,0	

Most of the coaches participating in the survey (70.7%, 99 participants) are not graduate of the related fields of School of Physical Education and Sports or Sports Sciences. P(80)

"I am not pleased to have a " C "license as a graduate of the School of Physical Education and Sports. The Graduates got a "B" license 5-6 years ago. I want to make arrangements in this regard. "

3.2 Findings Related to Coach Experiences

Table 5: Reasons Why Coaches Fail to Agree with a Team

The duration of which I had break in my coaching life.				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
I had no break.	59	42,1	42,1	42,1
The length of time I spent for various reasons as I rejected the offers.	24	17,1	17,1	59,3
The length of time I could not find a suitable team although I wanted to work.	35	25,0	25,0	84,3
The length of time I spent due to the changes made in the status / instructions related to the coaching certificate	8	5,7	5,7	90,0
The length of time I spent because a large number of people who has coaching license versus limited positions.	8	5,7	5,7	95,7
The length of time I spent a lot of time thinking that it would be more expensive to go to another city than my city where I live	4	2,9	2,9	98,6
The length of time I spent because the foreign coaches are in high demand.	2	1,4	1,4	100,0
Total	140	100,0	100,0	

42.1% (59) of the coaches participating in the survey stated that they were not idle in the current coaching career and 25% (35) stated that they could not find the team if they were in the position of working. 17,1% (24) stated that they rejected bids for various reasons. P(114) "Football coaches can be in a difficult situation because of unconscious managers. 20 thousand coaches are too much. The supply is more than demand for them. There is no justice." P(116) "There are many coaches. 150 of them can find work. The rest cannot make money because they are unemployed."

Table 6: Reasons Why Coaches Fail to Agree with a Team According To Their Licenses

		Which coaching license do you have?								Total	
		Grassroots C	UEFA B	UEFA A	UEFA Pro	Coach	TFF C	TFF B	TFF A		Any of these licenses + goalkeeper coaching
The duration of which I had break in my coaching life.	I had no break.	16	14	10	2	0	7	2	1	7	59
	The length of time I spent for various reasons as I rejected the offers.	3	2	7	2	0	5	4	1	0	24
	The length of time I could not find a suitable team although I wanted to work.	6	7	9	2	1	7	0	0	3	35
	The length of time I spent due to the changes made in the status / instructions related to the coaching certificate	1	1	1	1	0	2	0	0	2	8
	The length of time I spent because a large number of people who has coaching license versus limited positions.	1	1	4	2	0	0	0	0	0	8
	The length of time I spent a lot of time thinking that it would be more expensive to go to another city than my city where I live	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	2	4
	The length of time I spent because the foreign coaches are in high demand.	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2
Total		27	25	32	12	1	21	6	2	14	140

Of the coaches participating in the survey, of the 59 coaches who indicated that they have never been idle (unemployed), have following licenses.16 of them have TFF Grassroots C, 14 have UEFA B, 10 have UEFA license certificate. (There are 35 coaches who are not in the field of work) 9 of them have UEFA, 7 of them have UEFA B, 7 of them have TFF C coaching license. Of the 24 coaches who indicated that they rejected the offers for various reason; 7 of them have UEFA licenses and 5 of them have TFF C licenses.

Table 7: Situations in Which if Coaches Work or not in another Job
 When They Could not Agree with a Team

Have you ever been in another job when you were idle?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	61	43,6	43,6	43,6
	No	20	14,3	14,3	57,9
	I have never been idle	59	42,1	42,1	100,0
	Total	140	100,0	100,0	

43.6% (61) of coaches participating in the survey were found to have worked in other jobs to resume their lives when they were idle (unemployed). 14,6% (20) did not choose to work in another job. P(89) "I just want to work as a person who wants to do this work and I want to transfer all my time to this job."

Table 8: Work Experience of Coaches According to the Number of Contracts Terminated
 During the Season without Expiring Contract Times

		How many times in your coaching career was your contract terminated before the contract expired?				Total
		1-3	4-6	10 and more	I have never experienced this	
What kind of situation did you experience when your contract was terminated before your contract expires in the course of your current coaching career?	I have never experienced this	0	0	0	105	105
	I agreed with another team.	12	1	1	0	14
	I did not work at all until I signed up with another team, mostly next season	16	3	1	0	20
	I usually worked on another job with a lower income until I signed up with another team	1	0	0	0	1
Total		29	4	2	105	140

It has been seen that 75% (105) of the coaches participating in the survey have never been in contract termination before the contract expires. However, it is seen that 14.2% (20) did not work until the agreement with another team after the termination of the contract before the end of the contract in the season, and 14% (14) mostly agreed with another team in the same season. It is seen that coaches experience this situation a few times. P(134) "I want justice, I want to be understood. I'm looking for a manager who understands football. I just want to compete with coaches who have football background." P(135) "I want that the one who gets the job if he/she deserves it. I hope torpedo disappears"

Table 9: Team Search Initiatives According To Coaches' Positions In The Club

		I am looking for a team and I am attempting.		Total
		Yes	No	
I am currently working in the club position as	Coach	8	57	65
	Assistant coach	5	20	25
	Goalkeeper's coach	1	10	11
	I have a job other than coaching	14	10	24
	I am not doing any work right now	9	6	15
Total		37	103	140

Of the coaches participating in the survey, it was seen that 87.6% (57 of them) of the technical coaches in the club they were working with did not search for the team while they were still working and 58.9% of those who did not work and did not do any work except coaching.

Table 10: Job Search Initiatives Other Than Coaching According To Coaches' Positions In The Club

		I am looking for a job other than coaching and I am attempting.		Total
		Yes	No	
I am currently working in the club position as	Coach	13	52	65
	Assistant coach	5	20	25
	Goalkeeper's coach	1	10	11
	I have a job other than coaching	3	21	24
	I am not doing any work right now	4	11	15
Total		26	114	140

Of the coaches participating in the survey, it is seen that 80% of the coaches (52) and 80% of the assistant coaches (20) in the club they are working in are not currently engaged in a search for a job other than coaching while only 18.5% it seems that they are looking for a job and have initiatives.

P(39) "Football coaching in Turkey does not take place in a professional sense in every field. This does not seem to change much either." P(140) "I think there is no future for me in coaching. For this reason, I am dealing with a different business."

Table 11: Perception of Unemployment according To Positions of the coaches In Club

		I do not have a job right now but I'm ready to work		Total
		Yes	No	
I am currently working in the club position as	Coach	0	65	65
	Assistant coach	0	25	25
	Goalkeeper's coach	0	11	11
	I have a job other than coaching	1	23	24
	I am not doing any work right now	14	1	15
Total		15	125	140

93.3% (14 of them) of the coaches who do not have a job at the moment participating in the survey stated that They are ready to work. Those who did not do any work at the moment indicated that they were ready to work. P(24) "*I want better conditions, better materials, better players, better managers, more dedicated players.*"

Table 12: Professional Futures According to Coaches' Position in Clubs

		I gave up looking for a team.		Total
		Yes	No	
I am currently working in the club position as	Coach	26	39	65
	Assistant coach	7	18	25
	Goalkeeper's coach	8	3	11
	I have a job other than coaching	7	17	24
	I am not doing any work right now	5	10	15
Total		53	87	140

Among the coaches participating in the survey, 29.1% (7 of them) of those who did a job other than coaching and 33.3% (5 of them) of those who did not do any work, gave up looking for a team. P(29) "*Although they deserve a lot of things, they are not given the necessary value in Turkey, unfortunately.*"

3.3 Football Coaches' Views about the Profession

In general, football coaches stated that TFF and TFAD are more interested in the problems of working life of the coaches and requests for union establishment. The coaches, who emphasized the number of coaches, offered similar opinions on the

following coach training courses for coaches who are licensed to perform this profession:

P(85) *"More emphasis should be given to choosing a coach to do this job. That means you have to be more selective in coach selections (...) Those who can really do this job should be trained. Not only organize courses to give coaches licences. "*

P(87) *"Instruction of the coaches should not be done in the paid courses only. Personal development seminars must be organized and forced to be participate. Association of clubs inform the coaches."*

Coaches (64, 87, 136) stating their complaints about the placement of coach license fees have expressed their views that meetings should be organized to discuss coach problems (P109).

P(81) *"There must be insurance for coaches. It should be able to guarantee coaches' wages through official contract."* P(67) *"The social security aspect needs to be improved further"*, indicating signs of lack of informality and lack of social security on the football coaches market. Finally, it has been determined that there is a limit to the fact that coaches can conclude a maximum of two clubs in the same season, while the football coaches' base on which they are concerned about their unemployment experience can change as many coaches as the season demands.

4. Results and Discussion

It is seen that 1 of 2 coach who has TFF Grassroots C coaching license is in 2nd league, the other one is a coach in Premier league. However, the work field of the coach licensed by the TFF Grassroots C coaching license in the Training and Classification of Technical Managers Code of Practice according to the license documents of football coaches is *"Technical man in all age groups of amateur football activities, technical ladies in the women's leagues other than the top women's league, they can serve as coaches"*. The TFF C license document is the name of the previous TFF Grassroots C document, which indicates that the relevant coaches did not participate in the update courses^{vi}. Because the technical staff is classified according to courses or update courses, they graduate in current instruction and are assigned to their research areas. Football coaches point out the existence of a number of unlawful, and therefore illegal, practices in the labor market, where coaches' documents indicate that they are working in the respective leagues, although they are not eligible for classification. This can be interpreted as the fact that the coaches did not seem to be officially working while actually working. This, in turn, causes the coaches to be deprived of opportunities such as status, social and

^{vi} Instruction of Training and Classification of Technical Men, article 3.

economic security. The expressions in the coaches' views on the profession also emphasize this (P67, P81).

According to the coaching licenses of the football coaches participating in the research, it is seen that unregistered employment is a reflection of the football coaching occupation when the league is examined (Table 2). Findings from surveys conducted at different periods of coaching occupation and working conditions^{vii} show that such practices are a common practice in this profession. As such practices cannot be improved, It can also be interpreted as a source of considerations that football coaches are not considered to be a profession. With this interpretation, it is stated as Coach 3422.02, Coach 3422.04, Coach 3422.05 and football coach in the vocational dictionary of the Turkish Employment Agency^{viii}. But in general, the coaching profession is still not recognized as a profession by the parliament.

On the other hand, it is seen that some of the coaches with coaching license certificates that they can work in higher leagues (UEFA, UEFA, UEFA B) are working in amateur leagues (Table 2). This quantitative gap between work and worker is characterized by under employment in labor markets (Burke, 1997, Glyde, 1977). However, it will be insufficient to address the quality of coaches only with the ratings of their licenses. P(134)'s "*I want to compete only with those from within football*" and P(85)'s "*Those who can really do this job*" can be a projection of a thought that the coaching profession should be done by the coaches of more who have football history as players. Based on this, the playing football history of the coaches can be evaluated within the context of the evaluation of qualification with the scoring criteria of TFF. Table 3 shows that all of the coaches play football amateur, professional or both. Undoubtedly formal training is also a variant of the qualifications of coaches 29.3% (41 coaches) of the research group of graduates of football specialties of physical education and sports colleges or sport sciences faculties of sports education at the undergraduate level are made up by the fact that all of the graduates are professional or amateur football histories. It can be said that these coaches are equipped both in the sense of formal education and in the context of experience. When we look at the scoring charts of appealing coaching license courses, point of having professional football history is more than point of football education in the undergraduate level^{ix} supports our interpretation of evaluating playing football history in the context of quality. It can be said that this

^{vii} Football Coaching In The Context Of Underemployment 2013, An Evaluation On The Regulations Relating The Working Lives Of The Football Trainers In Turkey Considering The Economic Consequences 2016, see in References

^{viii} <https://esube.iskur.gov.tr/Meslek/meslek.aspx>, Date of Access: 09.11.2017.

^{ix} Instruction of Training and Classification of Technical Men, appendix4,appendix5

situation becomes chronic based on the detection of various types of coach under employment in the co-worker labor market in previous studies (Şaşmaz Ataçoğu and Zelyurt, 2013).

Findings related to the professional experience of coaches showed that a group of coach did not experience any unemployment while a coach was unemployed for various reasons (Table 5). "*Unemployment is a condition in which there is no opportunity to work in accordance with the workforce coming to the labor market to work in general*". 17.1% of the coaches participating in the study (24 coaches) have marked the reason for their idle time as "*I have spent time refusing offers for various reasons*". Unemployment in this sense is voluntary unemployment. In other words, the reasons for the unemployment of the worker are voluntarily unemployed, such as legal obligations, social practices, bargaining, adjustment delays or psychological reasons. Although the economic results are the same, theoretically, it cannot be said that the coaches are unemployed in such an experience (Canbey Özgüler, 2013). 40.8% of the coaches (35 + 8 + 8 + 4 + 2 = 57 coaches) are unemployed. According to the coaching licenses, when the coaches' experience of unemployment is taken into consideration, they are unemployed because they cannot find a team when they are in the labor market (Table 6). It is also noteworthy that the regulations on how the coaching profession is to be carried out are not seen as the cause of unemployment. This can be interpreted as a result of non-instructional practices in the market.

43.6% (61 coaches) of the coaches participating in the survey were found to have worked in other jobs in order to have their lives rescheduled when they were not working as a coach. Coaching is a profession that has no continuity in Turkey. In Turkey, especially in professional leagues coach exchange rates are quite high (Egesoy, 2010). During the 2017-2018 football seasons, there is a change of 7 technical teams in the 9th week in the Turkish Super League^x. During the 2016-2017 season, 46 technical directors served in TFF 1.League^{xi}. "*A person looking for a job while working in an irregular job is defined as being employed despite the job search activity*" (Lordoğlu and Özkaplan, 2005). Currently, 8 coaches, 5 assistant coaches and 1 goalkeeper coach working as a technical coach in a club were found to be in the team and attempted to intervene despite being employed. If this is related to the coach change rates, it can be said that the coaches are always faced with unemployment and therefore they are in search of a job. Nonetheless, it appears that there is no attempt to seek employment outside of the professions of the coaches, whether in employment or not (Table 10).

^x <http://aa.com.tr/tr/futbol/super-lig-avrupaya-fark-atti/948140>, Date of Access:09.11.2017

^{xi} <http://www.milliyet.com.tr/tff-1-lig-de-sadece-3-teknik-adam--2455579-skorerhaber/>, Date of Access:10.11.2017

It has been seen that most of the coaches that make up the sampling group have not had the experience of terminating the contract before the end of the season. However, it is also seen that the coaches who have experienced this have either agreed with another team in the same season or next season. This finding once again confirms that the coaching profession is a profession that has no continuity in Turkey.

Among the coaches participating in the survey, 29.1 (7) of those who did a job other than coaching and 33.3 (5) of those who did not do any work and gave up looking for a team to work with. It seems that these coaches seem to be hopeless now. In other words, the psychological cost of not seeking results from these negotiations can be included in addition to some material costs such as looking for a team, making phone calls with travel, club managers, managers, footballers. It seems that coaches who have been discouraged when the unemployment period is long can give up after a while.

In brief, the football coaches' social and economic insecurity caused by unintelligent practices; at the same time the number of victims created by these instructions, where the coaches are classified and their work area and duration are determined; long periods of unemployment and feelings of employment security even though they are working in a team; the possibility of being unemployed at any moment; it has been seen that they have had a long experience of passing through stages to practice their profession.

The performance of football coaches' professions is influential on their professional performances and therefore the performance of the teams. In parallel with sportive performance, the economic value of both the football market itself and the football labor market will be affected positively or negatively. It seems necessary to take account of market disruptions related to ongoing employment and unemployment that arise in the context of the experience of football coaches, an important element of the football labor market. In the final analysis, it is suggested that we try to make football coaching a legitimate profession, as requested by the coaches involved in the study. This will have a direct impact on the solution of the challenges that surround the profession of football coaching, which is the power of an enterprise to pass the misconception.

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